

Tables of Categories Similarity Analysis

Figure 14: Faced Difficulties Code Relations - Part 1

Figure 15: Faced Difficulties Code Relations - Part 2

Figure 16: Faced Difficulties Code Relations - Part 3

Figure 17: Future Possibilities Code Relations

Figure 18: Perceived Benefits Code Relations - Part 1

Figure 19: Perceived Benefits Code Relations - Part 2

Figure 20: Perceived Benefits Code Relations - Part 3

Figure 21: PRISE Qualities Code Relations - Part 1

Figure 22: PRISE Qualities Code Relations - Part 2

Figure 23: PRISE Qualities Code Relations - Part 3

Figure 24: Performed Tasks Code Relations - Part 1

Figure 25: Performed Tasks Code Relations - Part 2

Figure 26: Performed Tasks Code Relations - Part 3

Lista de Códigos	Highlights	Atomizing the steps	Facilitates the extension revision	Systematic framework	Encourages contact with domain experts
Highlights					
Atomizing the steps					
Facilitates the extension revision					
Systematic framework					
Encourages contact with domain exper					
Level of organization					
Organizes the information					
Organizes the concepts			2		
Self-explanatory process					
Iterative process					
Reflection of the concepts					
Promotes the reuse of already publishe					4
Grounded tasks					
Necessary tasks					

Figure 27: Highlights Code Relations - Part 1

Lista de Códigos	Level of organization	Organizes the information	Organizes the concepts	Self-explanatory process	Iterative process
Highlights					
Atomizing the steps					
Facilitates the extension revision			2		
Systematic framework					
Encourages contact with domain exper					
Level of organization					2
Organizes the information					
Organizes the concepts					
Self-explanatory process					
Iterative process	2				
Reflection of the concepts					
Promotes the reuse of already publishe					2
Grounded tasks		2			
Necessary tasks		2			

Figure 28: Highlights Code Relations - Part 2

Lista de Códigos	Reflection of the concepts	Promotes the reuse of already published elements	Grounded tasks	Necessary tasks
Highlights				
Atomizing the steps				
Facilitates the extension revision				
Systematic framework				
Encourages contact with domain exper		4		
Level of organization				
Organizes the information			2	2
Organizes the concepts				
Self-explanatory process				
Iterative process		2		
Reflection of the concepts				
Promotes the reuse of already publishe				
Grounded tasks				2
Necessary tasks			2	

Figure 29: Highlights Code Relations - Part 3